

Comparing the Accuracy of Different Sky Luminance Meters for Light Pollution Detection

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ABSTRACT

Light pollution is the excessive use of artificial light at night, also known as ALAN. Effects ranging from altering wildlife patterns, increasing adverse human health effects such as cancer and disturbed sleep patterns, as well as costing nations billions of dollars, light pollution is an ecological and economic hurdle, and many have come up with ways to quantify its amounts and see how it is affecting different parts of the world. Several devices and softwares have been developed to contribute to citizen science that helps visualize how light pollution has spread. The Sky Quality Meter (SQM) and Dark Sky Meter app on iPhone were used in this experiment to identify whether these devices are reliable when conducting light pollution data, with an emphasis on the app to test if it is a source that can be both consumer friendly and accurate. The Dark Sky Meter app provided results that were not within the hypothesized 0.4 mag/arcsec^2 value. In clear conditions, the measurements of the app compared to the SQM came the closest to the hypothesized value, with a range of between $0.56\text{-}0.905 \text{ mag/arcsec}^2$ difference. The concerning differences in values came when the sky was extremely illuminated with either a visible moon or a complete overcast, with a much greater variation range between $0.695\text{-}4.05 \text{ mag/arcsec}^2$ detected, depending on the specific weather conditions evaluated. This shows that the Dark Sky Meter app shows too great of an inaccurate variation compared to the SQM to be reliable for light pollution detection.

Keywords: *Artificial Light at Night, Sky Quality Meter, light pollution*

1. INTRODUCTION

Nearly every person living in either Europe or the U.S lives under skies that are approximately 10% brighter than how they naturally occur (Dutfield, 2022). As of 2016, it was discovered that nearly 80% of Americans cannot see the Milky Way (Greenfieldboyce, 2016). While a few countries still live under ideal night time viewing conditions, in regions such as Europe and the U.S, 99% of those populations live under some amount of skyglow (National Geographic Society, 2023).

Figure 1. Skyglow is the yellow coloring found in the sky above the city (Image from Kobi Lighting Studio).

Skyglow (*Figure 1*) is the increased apparent brightness of the night sky, deriving from the excess photons colliding with different air particles. This is most notable in areas with intense lighting (U.S Department of Energy, 2023). Skyglow is one of the few byproducts of light pollution plaguing the world. Light sources such as improper street lighting, electronic advertising, factories, sports lighting, and any non-natural sources contribute to light pollution

(Bult, 2023). Light pollution has become a significant issue all around the globe in the past few decades. Nearly 100 years ago, it was estimated that just about anyone could go outside and view the Milky Way with ease. Now, one-third of the world cannot view the Milky Way at all (Ramlagan, 2016). This alone inhibits the ability for astronomers to observe the night sky, limiting the amount of ideal dark sky sites for astronomical observation.

Ecosystems have suffered from the effects of ALAN, with many species experiencing various altered behaviors. Sea turtles have become one of the main species of concern, as they need quiet and dark places along shorelines to nest (DarkSky International, 2014). ALAN from various homes, hotels, and businesses around the beach discourages sea turtles from nesting properly. New hatchlings also depend on moonlight to navigate their way back to the ocean, but ALAN can disorient these turtles, pulling them inland and succumbing to death (Bult, 2023). Experiments on different animals such as rats and hamsters have shown that even slightly elevated levels of artificial light suppress melatonin production, disrupting systems such as endocrine pathways (Emmer et al, 2018). Many adverse health effects in humans have also shown connections to ALAN. Increased risks of certain cancers including lung, breast, and prostate, have been found to have relation with exposure to excess ALAN (Al-Naggar & Anil, 2016).

Besides the many adverse biological concerns associated with ALAN, countries such as the U.S are spending an excessive amount of money to keep cities illuminated, with one-third of lighting in the U.S being wasted, costing close to 2 billion dollars used annually (Sea Turtle Conservancy, 2023). The goal of many organizations that focus on decreasing light pollution is to quantify it with citizen data, adding to further research on how ALAN is perceived in different areas. Using this data helps with addressing several aspects of light pollution, such as implementing laws restricting the type and/or amount of ALAN used in an area and observing how different ecosystems with varying amounts of light pollution behave. Therefore, it is crucial that there are accurate, and consumer friendly, devices out there for citizens to access and use to contribute to citizen science.

The Sky Quality Meter (SQM) is a handheld device that is used by many astronomers to measure the brightness of night skies to identify ideal dark sky locations, and to send in data to contribute to the continuous studies on light pollution. It measures in magnitude per arcsecond ($\text{mag}/\text{arcsec}^2$), which is a value that describes the brightness of an arcsecond of a sky in comparison to a certain star magnitude (Sky Quality Meter, 2023). The downfall of this device is the cost is \$155. In recent years, more affordable and consumer accessible alternatives such as the Dark Sky Meter app on iPhone have been released to perform the same task as a SQM. This app only costs \$1.99 on the Apple app store. This experiment explored the question of whether the Dark Sky Meter app is a reliable and accurate measure of sky brightness in comparison to the SQM-L. It is hypothesized that the readings from the Dark Sky Meter app will measure no more than $0.4 \text{ mag}/\text{arcsec}^2$ error, proving to be an accurate device for light pollution measurement. The unihedron instructions for the SQM state that between each calibrated SQM, the difference in precision is typically $\pm 10\%$ of each reading taken. 0.4 was chosen because there is bound to be a slight variation between devices due to the different technology that is utilized to sense sky brightness.

2. METHODOLOGY

For this study, four locations were tested with varying levels of sky visibility. These locations were chosen by evaluating their classification on the Bortle Scale, which is a nine value scale that measures the sky's brightness and star visibility, with Class 1 being the darkest skies and Class 9 being the most illuminated skies by ALAN (Bortle, 2021). A light pollution map (Light Pollution Map, 2023) was also used as a general reference for finding different locations using the listed Bortle scale and $\text{mag}/\text{arcsec}^2$ for each spot (**Figure 2**). While light pollution maps like this one give relative ideas of the sky brightness levels in different regions, the data is usually outdated, such as the one listed below with data from 2015. It is important to collect current measurements to add to update databases and see the progression of light pollution over a certain time period. The locations chosen were the Joplin Regional Airport, Carl Junction High School, Downtown Joplin, and the Ndauwa Residence (**Figure 3**).

Figure 2. Light pollution map uses general data from 2015 to generate an idea of the brightness of the sky in different parts of the world (Image by Light Pollution Map).

Figure 3. Map depicting the areas of each location (Map by Tiffany Ndaawa).

Measurements were taken in between the hours of 7:00-8:30 pm with both the SQM and the Dark Sky Meter app. The sky is dark enough for proper data collection during this time and data collection was more accessible and safe during this time interval. Photos with the iPhone 12 were taken at each site to provide a visual representation of the night skies at the time of data collection (**Figure 4**).

Figure 4. Example photos taken of the night sky at indicated locations during the study (Photos taken by Tiffany Ndauwa).

It was aimed to capture data with varying weather conditions, specifically cloud cover, as clouds reflect light and the amount of skyglow is amplified (Public Library of Science, 2011). At least eight different types of data were collected at each location, with three of the nights being completely clear, three being clear but with a substantial amount of the moon visible during collection, and two with completely overcast skies. Overall, a total of 32 different trials took place during this experiment.

3. RESULTS

Eight days of data were collected over a five week period. The Joplin Airport and Carl Junction High School were the locations that were classified as darker locations, in comparison to Downtown Joplin and the Ndauwa Residence, which were the locations classified with brighter skies, as they were more centered in the city. Three days with clear skies, three days with clear skies and the moon visible, and two days with overcast clouds were measured. This data is displayed in **Figures 5-8**.

Figure 5: Graph of data at the Joplin Airport (Graph by Tiffany Ndauwa).

Figure 6: Graph of data at Carl Junction High School (Graph by Tiffany Ndauwa).

Figure 7: Graph of data in Downtown Joplin (Graph by Tiffany Ndauwa)

Figure 8: Graph of data at the Ndaauwa Residence (Graph by Tiffany Ndaauwa).

4. DISCUSSION

Overall, the differences in values between the SQM and app were greater than hypothesized. When analyzing the data sets for both devices during the days where the sky was clear with no interference from the moon, the variation in the values for both devices was the smallest. There was a range of 0.56-0.905 mag/arcsec² difference found between the averages of each device at each location tested on the days with clear skies. Variations between each device became smaller when testing the darker locations (Carl Junction High School and the Joplin Regional Airport) in comparison to the brighter sites (Downtown Joplin and the Ndaauwa Residence). For example, the difference of the averages between the SQM and app at Carl Junction High School with clear skies was 0.56 mag/arcsec². Whereas in Downtown Joplin, the difference between the averages were 0.905 mag/arcsec². However, when analyzing the data with brighter conditions such as overcast or an illuminated moon, the app struggled to produce accurate results. In overcast conditions, variation between the SQM and the app reached 2.48 mag/arcsec², with the app suggesting that the sky was significantly darker than what it was. Similar to the case of clear skies, the inaccuracies increased when measuring Downtown and the Ndaauwa Residence. For the Joplin Airport, the difference was 1.37 mag/arcsec², and for Carl Junction, the difference was

1.145 mag/arcsec². For Downtown Joplin, the difference was 2.48 mag/arcsec², and for the Ndaauwa Residence, the difference was 2.3 mag/arcsec².

The weather condition with the largest variation between averages was when the moon was 64% illuminated and in the view of the sensors of the devices. This is also when the trend of the darker locations having smaller variations did not apply. At the Joplin Airport, the difference in the averages was 4.05 mag/arcsec², and at Carl Junction High School, the difference was 3.715 mag/arcsec². This is a concerning difference in the app's data which cannot be used for accurate sky brightness measurement. Overall, this study shows that the Dark Sky Meter app was not a reliable tool for producing accurate sky brightness readings, especially when measuring in extremely bright conditions.

5. LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE STUDIES

One limitation of this study is that only two devices were tested, limiting the amount of variation in data and being able to analyze different options when it comes to measuring light pollution. Another limitation was working around the weather and moon phases and choosing the most optimal days for data collection in preferable conditions. One more limitation is that this study only tested skies on eight different days, which limits the amount of samples available for analysis.

In the future, the study should aim to test out more devices that can be used for light pollution measurement, as well as use different types of phones for the Dark Sky Meter app to test if the different cameras affect the results. Furthermore, a test on more types of weather as well as much darker locations or much brighter locations to provide greater variety in the types of sites tested. Lastly, there should be tests on more days to provide a greater sample set.

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REFERENCES

- Al-Naggar, Redhwan A. & Anil, Shirin. (2016, January). Artificial Light at Night and Cancer: Global Study. National Library of Medicine.
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC5454613/>
- Bortle, J. E. (2021, June 28). Gauging light pollution: the Bortle Dark-Sky Scale. Sky & Telescope.
<https://skyandtelescope.org/astronomy-resources/light-pollution-and-astronomy-the-bortle-dark-sky-scale/>
- Bult, M. (2023, April 27). Causes of Light Pollution. DarkSky International.
<https://darksky.org/resources/what-is-light-pollution/causes/>
- DarkSky International. (2014, September 4). Sea Turtle Conservation.
<https://darksky.org/resources/guides-and-how-tos/sea-turtle-conservation/>
- Dutfield, S. (2022, April 5). Light pollution: Environmental impact, health risks and facts. livescience.com. <https://www.livescience.com/light-pollution>
- Emmer, K. M., Russart, K. L. G., Walker, W. H. II, Nelson, R. J., & DeVries, A. C. (2018). Effects of light at night on laboratory animals and research outcomes. Behavioral Neuroscience, 132(4), 302–314. <https://doi.org/10.1037/bne0000252>
- Greenfieldboyce, N. (2016, June 10). Light pollution hides milky way from 80 percent of North Americans, Atlas shows. NPR.
<https://www.npr.org/sectionsthetwo-way/2016/06/10/481545778/light-pollution-hides-milky-way-from-80-percent-of-north-americans-atlas-shows>
- Light pollution map. (n.d.). <https://www.lightpollutionmap.info/#zoom=7.34&lat=37.4657&lon=-92.6446&state=eyJiYXNlbWFwIjoiTGF5ZXJCaW5nUm9hZCIsIm92ZXJsYXkiOiJ3YV8yMDE1Iiwib3ZlcmxheWNvbG9yIjpmYWxzZSwib3ZlcmxheW9wYWwNpdHkiOjYwLCJmZWV0dXJlc29wYWNpdHkiOjg1fQ==>

National Geographic Society. (2023, October 19). Light Pollution. National Geographic.
<https://education.nationalgeographic.org/resource/light-pollution/>

Public Library of Science. (2011, March 3) "Clouds amplify ecological light pollution."
ScienceDaily. ScienceDaily, =
<www.sciencedaily.com/releases/2011/03/110302171312.htm>.

Ramlagan, N. (2016, June 9). One third of people cannot see the milky way | American
Association for the Advancement of Science (AAAS). American Association for the
Advancement of Science (AAAS).
[https://www.aaas.org/news/one-third-people-cannot-see-milky-way#:~:text=One%20Third%20of%20People%20Cannot,the%20Advancement%20of%20Science%20\(AAAS\)](https://www.aaas.org/news/one-third-people-cannot-see-milky-way#:~:text=One%20Third%20of%20People%20Cannot,the%20Advancement%20of%20Science%20(AAAS))

Sea Turtle Conservancy (n.d.). Information About Sea Turtles: Threats from Artificial Lighting.
Retrieved November 16, 2023, from
<https://conserveturtles.org/information-sea-turtles-threats-artificial-lighting/#:~:text=Lighting%20near%20the%20shore%20also,is%20usually%20over%20the%20ocean.>

Sky Quality Meter

(n.d.).<http://www.unihedron.com/projects/darksky/faq.php#:~:text=The%20term%20magnitudes%20per%20square,square%20arcsecond%20of%20the%20sky.>

U.S Department of Energy: What is Sky Glow? (n.d.). Energy.gov. Retrieved November 16,
2023, from
<https://www.energy.gov/eere/ssl/text-alternative-version-what-sky-glow#:~:text=Light%20traveling%20into%20the%20sky,night%20sky%20or%20sky%20glow.>